

Ecological Education in Preschool Education

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Abstract: This article describes the formation of ecological culture in preschool children, the forms of ecological education, the characteristics of environmental education and its importance.

Keywords: environmental education, organization of preschool education, nature, age of preschool education, environmental knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, it has become one of the important areas of preschool pedagogy and is implemented in many preschool educational organizations in the country. Almost all modern complex, basic programs cover sections on environmental education of preschool children, and there are a number of additional programs.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

All-Russian, regional, city conferences on environmental protection are held, special courses are taught at pedagogical universities and colleges, environmental teachers have appeared in a number of preschool educational institutions. Everything looks good. However, experience shows that not all problems in this area have been solved yet. There are inconsistencies in understanding the terms "ecology", "ecological education (education)", defining the goals, tasks, content and methods of environmental education. For example, sometimes kindergartens go the simplest way, they begin to change the names of traditional classes in order to introduce preschool children to the surrounding world, nature and teach the moral qualities of the child to "ecological" ones. What is the reason for this situation? Experiment in your team (of course, the experiment does not reflect the complexity of the problem, but it makes you think).

Ecology as a special field of science appeared in the 19th century. At that time, it was only part of zoology and looked at the relationship of animals, communities with each other and with the environment. The word "ecology" itself was coined by the German naturalist Ernst Haeckel. Defined as the science of living organisms and their interactions with the environment. Translated from Greek, "ecology" is the science of home, dwelling ("oikos" - home, "logos" - science). Now this direction is called biological or classical ecology. Of course, ecology is not an easy science. But in order to understand this and work meaningfully in the field of environmental education, you must first remember the four laws formulated by the American scientist Barry Commoner in a popular form:

These laws basically determine our existence, although we often do not question it. Information about the environment is increasingly added to our lives, but we do not always have enough information to evaluate it correctly.

Sometimes ordinary information about the amount of various emissions into the environment or a warning about the increase in air pollution on quiet days causes panic and gives rise to various rumors that are not related to the real situation. . At the same time, we live near sources of environmental damage, unaware of their effects on our health, grow vegetables near highways with heavy traffic pollution, swim and fish in rivers near sewage pipes. , we will grow our garden. the amount of pesticides, we create garbage dumps near our houses and many other things that should not happen under any circumstances. At the same time, we believe that only the government can influence the environment, but not ourselves, and nothing depends on us. This point of view is mainly related to the fact that for a long time there was no place for ecology in most educational institutions. In addition, it is precisely the attitude of consumers to nature, the desire to conquer and improve it with your own will that has been cultivated. It is very difficult for adults who have been brought up in such positions to change their attitude towards the environment. Hope for the young generation, we have to educate it anew.

With the development of society, ecology has become more and more socially important, and in our century it has gone out of the scope of natural sciences. In the middle of the twentieth century, ecology became widely popular among all people, regardless of specialization. It has become a science that helps people to survive, to make their living environment suitable for existence. Unfortunately, society realized this when the negative consequences of people's attitude towards nature were already visible, when there was almost no corner of nature left on the planet, and the condition of the habitat had a negative effect on the health of many people. In recent years, new areas of ecology are rapidly developing - social ecology, applied ecology, human ecology, video ecology, etc., which consider the relationship between society and nature.

From the "organism - environment" problem, ecology approached the "man - nature" problem. At this stage of development, we realized the role and necessity of environmental education from a very early age. When choosing the content of environmental education for preschool children, the existence of different areas of ecology is taken into account. We should not forget the ideological importance of ecology, therefore, its connection with all aspects of life - history, culture, geography, etc. At the same time, the boundaries of this concept should not be violated, it should be used as a fashion trend without any reason. Nowadays, the word "ecology" has become extremely popular and, as a rule, it is used together with words such as "disaster", "danger", "crisis", which are not very pleasant for us. In addition, this concept is used in the above-mentioned expressions "ecology of spirit", "ecology of music", "ecology of speech", "ecology of culture", which often has a new meaning that is completely far from its original meaning. Idi Of course, each of these terms carries its own meaning, but the word "ecology" is often used for a fashionable, beautiful sound.

Thus, dealing with the problems of "ecology of the heart" (i.e. ethics, moral problems), educators focus on the most important educational aspect - the formation of personality, including the formation of the child's attitude to nature and the surrounding world. But ecology as a science has nothing to do with it. Undoubtedly, the moral principle is very important for the ecological upbringing of the child, but it is one of its aspects, even if it is very important. Moreover, all the laws of nature are not moral from the human point of view. A person can have perfect moral qualities, but without knowing the laws of nature, he performs actions against the environment. For example, following the laws of human morality, a child picks up a chick that has fallen from its nest to save it. After that, in most cases, the chick dies. Therefore, it is necessary to combine moral qualities with elementary ecological knowledge, so that human behavior towards nature will be ecologically appropriate.

You can often hear phrases like "bad (" good ", " terrible ") ecology." But it is important to remember that ecology as a science cannot be good or bad (we do not say "bad" physics or

mathematics). You can only evaluate the environmental situation, the situation (normal, bad, dangerous, safe, etc.).

CONCLUSION

Therefore, through the development of environmental education in preschool children, a foundation is created for the formation of their love for nature and mastery of natural sciences in the future. Environmental education for children and the use of modern methods have good results. This technology is gradually developing in our country. Through this, it is possible to further improve children's mastery and organize an interesting, new educational process.

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